

Egypt's Role in Arab Diplomacy and its Foreign Policy in Regional Conflicts.

EGYPT AND THE MIDDLE-EAST

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Egypt and the Middle East

Introduction

Egypt falls on the Arab region and Arab states are Muslim states and share some history due to its region, not only Egypt but other states in the Arab region have a conflict on the Palestinian territory occupied by Israel as the Arabs believe that it's an Islamic territory while the Israelis believe that it's the holy land of Jewish people as mentioned in their holy books.

Both fight for their holy lands and some argue that Jewish are true Arabs which have old history in this land some argue that this land is a Muslim territory having different ideologies a conflict rises between Egypt and Israel.

Scholar Cannot agree on the exact origins of Arab Nationalism, nor can they agree on an exact answer to the question "Who is an Arab?". Much of the discourse in the Arab world from the 1940s through the 1960s focused on the subject of Arab nationalism or, more exactly pan-Arabism extended from about the mid-1950s to the 1967 Arab-Israel war. In 1978 Fouad Ajami, a prominent scholar of middle eastern studies wrote a highly influential article titled "The End of Pan-Arabism" and in an essay in Foreign Affairs contended that pan-Arabism, an "idea that has dominated the political consciousness of the modern Arabs is nearing its end, if it is not already a thing of the past."

Some disagreed with Ajami's assertion or you can say Ajami's argument and believe Arab nationalism is still a powerful political force, despite facing challenges since the 1970s like Egypt's peace treaty with Israel and the rise of Islamic fundamentalism. This debate highlights the importance of Gamal Abdel Nasser's role in promoting Arab nationalism.

In the Political Biography of Nasser Robert Stephen States:

"Both Ataturk and he tried and failed to transform their dictatorships into something more democratic. Both were defeated in this endeavor by their own reluctance in the last resort to give up real power as well as by the authoritarian traditions of their countries. Nasser demonstrated an opposition to the intrusion of religion into politics almost as strong as that of Ataturk, but he made no attempt to follow Ataturk's example in the disestablishment of Islam, except in the important reform of the application of Sharia law. Nasser recognized the place of Islam in the state and in society and in Egyptian and Arab culture and was careful not to press for changes regarding issues of women's rights and family planning too hard or too fast".

(Bishku, 1988)

Methodology

The methodology of this research is based on historical analysis. It's a review consisting concept of many authors. The data includes information from Books, journal articles by different authors to Study Egypt's foreign policy e.g., Nasser's Role in the Arab world (1988) by Bishku, Egypt and the Arabs (1990) by Lorenz, etc.

Research Objective

The Main Objective of this research is to study how Egypt's Foreign policy was interconnected with its geographical location, how Egypt's foreign policy evolved in Arabs Diplomacy and how it has played a significant role in regional conflicts like the regional conflicts were or are mostly due to its geographical location although it benefited but also there were conflicts so the Egypt's role will be studied in this research.

Research Question

Research questions for this article are to study, How Nasser's era impacted Egypt's foreign policy?, How Geographical location of Egypt helped Egypt in making or adopting new foreign policy?, How Geographical location of Egypt emerged conflicts for Egypt?, How Egypt faced Challenges since old times?, How Egypt played a role in Arab?, What was Egypt's Role in Regional Conflicts?

Significance of the study

This study Explains how Egypt's problem are due to its geographical location and how it's historical analysis for understanding Egypt's policy and its role in Arab diplomacy and how Egypt deals regional conflicts and it impacts its foreign policy and how Egypt can play a positive role in policy-making. The study's importance lies in its ability to explain current problems and provide useful lessons for future policy-making.

Statement of the Problem

Egypt's foreign policy has been much affected by its physical situation. From Egypt's links with its neighbours to its role in regional and foreign events, this impact has show itself in a range of ways. Still, the exact kind of this effect is complex and diverse. Egypt's geographic situation has, on the one hand, given it several perks such access to the Mediterranean Sea and power over the Suez Canal. Egypt's situation has, however, also made it vulnerable to outside risks like political interference and attack. Furthermore, Egypt's physical situation has affected its internal politics, hence building its national character and relations with its own people.

Though a lot of research on Egyptian foreign policy is already in print, a full study focussing especially on the function of geography is still needed. This study will seek to fill this gap by giving a full investigation of how Egypt's physical situation has affected its foreign policy. By doing this, it will try to provide a more complicated picture of Egypt's place in the international order and in the Arab world.

Background of Egypt

Geographical Background

Geography is one of the variables on which a country's attitude is made up towards the outside world. Even that varies in its impact as technological changes like rapid transportation and instant communication.

(Lorenz, 1990)

Example: Think about Russia's past interaction with its neighbors. Russia's strategic thinking and foreign policy for millennia have been greatly affected by its large territory and restricted access to warm-water ports.

Tensions and disputes with surrounding nations result from a drive for territorial expansion and control over important access points driven by this geographic reality.

Historically, Egypt was considered an African rather than an Arab state. Pharaonic Egypt was nothing but an African state, and its relations with south of the Nile valley and Central Africa have continued ever since. It is possible to view the geopolitical regional relations between Egypt and the states of the African Horn and the Nile basin in such a way that they could be considered conducive to cooperation in peacetime, but a point of pressure that might threaten the Egyptian entity in case of war or the threat of it.

(Hassan & Rasheedy, 2007)

Natural Territories Like Nile River served as natural defenses and can help to provide sufficient food, deserts and mountains to protect its territory. Having these territorial benefits Egypt didn't take part in sea wars like Britain and France because they lack timber or ship building material and it was harder to import that from other states and they couldn't master building the Nile river drainage and irrigation system, which made the control of Egypt on their territory a bit lesser.

This impacted as the Egypt's trade, communication, and presence in global level reduced. Until the twentieth century, the annual Nile floods dominated Egyptian life. The Nile required extensive drainage and irrigation systems; these in turn called for capital, technical expertise, and coordinated control of labor. The result was the rise of a highly centralized political and economic authority. As the pharaohs came to exercise absolute power over their subjects, habits and expectations formed that help to explain the exceptional latitude that modern Egyptian leaders have had in the formulation of national policy, especially in the area of foreign affairs.

For example, nothing so irritated Egyptians as President Sadat's proposal to divert Nile water to Israel's Negev Desert in exchange for concessions on Jerusalem. The Nile is Egypt; it is not a bargaining chip in international politics. Other national traits can be traced to the self-contained nature of Nile villages and to the attunement of rural life to the rhythm of the river's rise and fall. The Egyptian tendency toward complacency and, at times,

isolationism combines with a remarkable rootedness to the soil, leading to conservatism and a strong attachment to traditional social values.⁴ These attitudes are characteristic not only of the peasantry but of the millions who moved to the cities in the last two generations, among them Nasser and Sadat.

(Lorenz, 1990)

Foreign Relations Background

When the upper and lower Egypt were united under strong pharaohs, Egypt not only successfully defended itself but also enlarged, its frontiers against Asians.

Most of the pharaohs were not interested in spreading Egyptian culture, acquiring and settling foreign territories. Their civilization was centered on the Nile and their were limited objectives for their art and religion, as their ideology was totally based on that life is comfortable only after death.

Coming back from ancient time to seventh century the Egypt's foreign relations with Phoenicians and with the Greece reached new heights The Greeks found the Egyptians more interesting than the Egyptians found them. "Before the impact of the foreign life which thus flowed in upon Egypt, the Egyptian showed himself entirely unmoved, and held himself aloof, fortified behind his ceremonial purity and his inviolable reserve." ¹³ The accounts of Greek-Egyptian relations in antiquity that Herodotus and other Greek travelers provide offer fascinating insights into the enduring nature of national character. On the one side were the Greeks, curious, cosmopolitan, and intrigued by the presumed wisdom of pharaonic civilization (hidden from them by hieroglyphics they could not decipher on the other were the Egyptians, self-contained, dignified, and disinterested in cultures alien to their own. The final pharaonic thrust into Asia came in 608 B.C., when Egypt once again invaded Syria and went on to rule over land reaching to the Euphrates. Two years later the Egyptian army was routed by Nebuchadnezzar of Babylon. A few last Egyptian forays against the Babylonians followed, after which the brief moment of resurgent Egyptian empire came to a close. From the Persian conquest in 525 B.C. until Nasser's coup d'etat in 1952, Egypt was ruled by foreigners.

(Lorenz, 1990)

Formerly I [Nasser] believed neither in the Arabs nor in Arabism. Each time that you or someone else spoke to me of the Arabs, I laughed at what you said. I could not believe the Arab peoples capable of anything. The Palestine war [of 1948] strengthened even more my conviction concerning the powerlessness of the Arabs. But when I realized all the potential possessed by the Arab States! That is what made me change my mind.

(Bishku, 1988)

Regional Conflict

Egypt's Foreign Policy In Regional Conflicts

The 1922-1952 Period and Egyptian Foreign Policy Behavior It has been argued that the geographic location of the Nile River represents a major asset, which has naturally and historically shaped Egyptian foreign policy since the dawn of independence (Brunnee and Toope 202: 148). Egyptian geo-strategic objectives during the period from 1922 to 1952 focused on three issues. First, there was an interest in establishing cordial bilateral relations between Sudan and Egypt. The Egyptian-Sudanese bilateral relations guaranteed uninterrupted flow of Nile waters and in the process protected Egypt's historical and acquired rights. Indeed, the idea of binding Sudan to Egypt is deeply rooted in Egyptian political history, which is premised on the desire for the historical integration between Egypt and Sudan. Specifically, the policy is based on the age-old view that whoever controls the Sudan, threatens Egyptian geo-strategic water policy interests.

Egyptian-Sudanese linkages date back to 1899 when Britain established a condominium over the control of southern Sudan. The question of Sudan became one of the central issues in British-Egyptian relations during that period before the revolution of 1952

Second, the Egyptian-British Nile River treaty of 1929 took cognisance of Egyptian historical interests with regard to the Nile waters (Caponera 1993:657-659). The 1929 agreement provided for a clear sharing of the Nile River waters. For example, the treaty incorporated Egyptian historical needs by setting aside the bulk of the flow of the waters to Cairo, that is, by allocating to Egypt a share of 48 million cubic meters in return for four million cubic meters for Sudan.

The agreement concluded in London in 1934 between Britain (on behalf of Tanganyika) and Belgium (on behalf of Rwanda and Burundi) regarding the River Kagera, which flows into Lake Victoria, recognized the equitable utilization of the river in such a way that would not jeopardise the interests of other fluvial states. Third, Britain and Egypt also entered into a bilateral agreement in 1932 on the use of the Jabal elawleya reservoir. The storage capacity of this project was estimated to be 3.5 million cubic meters annually.

(Hassan & Rasheedy, 2007)

Although Sadat's domestic and foreign policy was to differ drastically from Nasser's, both of them started facing the problem of sovereignty. Nasser's first concern was to free Egypt from British occupation; Sadat's to liberate Sinai from the Israelis. Launching the October War, achieving Egyptian sovereignty at least partly over Sinai, provided Sadat with legitimacy and confidence to transform Egypt's domestic scene and to direct its foreign policy toward new orientations.

Since assuming power in October 1970 and until October 1973, Sadat remained committed to the basic lines of Nasser's foreign policy, particularly in relation to the Soviet Union and the United States. He went even further

in continuing the special relationship with the Soviet Union by signing a treaty of friendship and cooperation with the Soviet Union in May 1971, something Nasser had been reluctant to do. However, during this period he also took two steps whose full meaning and significance was to be revealed afterwards. The first was his overthrow of the group of politicians known for their loyalty to Nasser and their ideological commitment to the Soviet Union. The second step was his demand in July 1972 for the withdrawal of foreign military experts in Egypt a decision which confused even his own advisors and was regarded by Henry Kissinger as a free cost loss for the Russians.

As noted earlier, launching the October War and restoring respect for Egypt provided Sadat with the mandate to implement his vision for future commitments and foreign policy choices, and towards the Arab-Israeli conflict in particular. In this regard, Sadat was motivated by two major concepts: first, that wars and military confrontations had exhausted themselves as a means of solving the Middle East conflict; and secondly, that the United States, with its leverage and commitments to Israel, was the only power that could help in reaching a political settlement.¹³ Sadat was also convinced that Egypt was the natural leader among the Arab States, and wherever Egypt led the others would follow.¹⁴ In this framework Sadat remained firm on two issues, Egyptian sovereignty and territorial integrity, and the need to address the legitimate rights of the Palestinian people.

Sadat's peace offensive culminated with the conclusion of the Camp David accords in 1978. The Egyptian component, the peace treaty with Israel in 1979, was to have far-reaching repercussions on Egypt's relations with the Arab world and on relations with the Soviet Union.

In November 1978, the Arab summit in Baghdad recommended that Arab countries sever relations with Egypt. The Arab League transferred its seat from Cairo to Tunisia. Further attempts were made to isolate Egypt from other regional gatherings such as the Organization of African Unity and the non-aligned movement. Thanks to Egypt's credentials in these groups, the OAU and the non-aligned countries with the exception of handful of ideologically oriented countries sustained Egypt's position

Egypt's attitude towards the Israeli invasion of Lebanon in 1982 gave substance to Egypt's commitments to the basic Arab rights. Following the Sabra and Shatila massacres in particular, Egypt recalled its ambassador to Israel, insisting that his return would be conditional on Israeli withdrawal from Lebanon. This episode assured Egypt's goodwill towards the Palestinians, when Egypt helped in evacuating PLO from Tripoli in Lebanon a gesture followed by gradual political contacts and reconciliation with the PLO.

As a signal of remaining faithful to broader Arab commitments, Egypt supported Iraq in its conflict with Iran and provided Iraq with military assistance short of military personnel. The gradual reconciliation of Egypt with the Arab world culminated in the Amman Arab summit in November 1987, which endorsed the resumption of diplomatic relations with Egypt and subsequently the return of the Arab League to its original seat in Cairo in May 1991

(Shalaby, 1992)

Due to domestic needs and the pursuit of a pragmatic foreign policy, Egypt avoided, officially at least, support for Sudan in the struggle against southern insurgents for fear that such support would negatively affect Cairo's regional and continental interests (Himdan 1987: 940). On the geopolitical and geo-strategic front, the active role played by Egyptian diplomacy in mutual understanding between Ethiopia and Sudan, which culminated into the normalization of the two countries' relations, is a clear indication of Egypt's neutral position in the region. Similarly, it can be argued that a balanced and flexible policy pursued by Egypt with respect to the intra state civil wars and inter-state conflicts demonstrate Cairo's pragmatism in the region.

In addition to the civil war in Sudan, internal Ethiopian conflict with the national movement for the Eritrean people, the Ethiopian-Eritrean war of 1998-2000, and Ethiopian direct conflict with and involvement in Somalia regarding the Ogaden area since the 1960s have necessitated careful consideration by the Egyptian foreign policy establishment. Specifically, Egyptian foreign policy-makers adopted positions that did not support one party against the other, irrespective of the legal claims. The decision by Egyptian foreign policy-makers to maintain regional peace and security is influenced by the desire to avoid any conflict with states of the Nile Basin, and especially with Ethiopia and Sudan.

(Hassan & Rasheedy, 2007)

Egypt's Role in Arab Diplomacy

Sometimes the commonly accepted assumptions about a subject can be found to be incorrect by simply checking the basics. For the economic diplomacy of Egypt toward the Middle East, and the Middle East toward Egypt after Camp David, a lot can be learned from simply adding up the trade, remittance and aid data, graphing them over time, and thinking about what resulted.

(Sullivan, 1999)

The Muslim Brotherhood publicly attacks Sadat's regime with unusual vehemence. Why has the regime tolerated the MB so far, when it has not allowed other secular opposition groups to go that far? Is the MB capable in the foreseeable future of taking over power, say in the Iranian mode? As to the first question, Sadat's regime is understandably annoyed with the MB. Sadat is embarrassed by the escalating attack of al-Da'wa and al-Vtisam, but is in a predicament as to how to deal with them. He staked -his quest for legitimacy on his "democratization" drive and on adopting religious faith (al- Iman) as one of the regime's slogans. The MB has so far refrained from acts of violence of the kind committed by other fringe Islamic groups on its right and its left. Thus for Sadat to ban the MB or its publications would expose him as both antidemocratic and anti-Islamic. Nevertheless, he has not been totally helpless vis-à-vis the MB. On several occasions he counterattacked Muslim (and Christian)

fanaticism and insisted that religion and politics should remain separate.⁵⁸ He does not allow the formation of religious political parties. When one of the fringe Islamic groups engages in violence, the regime uses the occasion as a pretext to go on an all-out "overkill" against all Islamic groups.⁵⁹ Another regime tactic is occasional appeasement of the MB. Recently, for example, Sadat appointed two Muslim figures (one a former MB member and the other an MB sympathizer) to prominent state positions.⁶⁰ A special committee in the People's Assembly (Egypt's Parliament) has been formed to look into the adoption of the shari'ah as a framework for Egypt's legal system.

(Ibrahim, 1982)

There was a significant drop off in imports from Kuwait to Egypt from 1978 to 1982. But from 1982 to 1985 they had increased from about \$10 million to about \$90 million. Exports to Lebanon increased in 1978 to 1981. Imports from Lebanon, after a slight drop in 1978 to 1979, went upward in 1980 and 1981. Exports to and imports from Jordan pretty much vaporized for 1980-1983. By 1984, however, they showed steady growth for years to come. In the other hand, Libya and Syria shut off imports from Egypt. The only recognizable trade is in imports from Libya in 1983-1988. But that was extremely small. Unfortunately for Egypt it probably did not profit fully from the trade benefits of the sharp increases in oil revenues in the GCC in the time period 1978 to 1981. It did, however, still gain with increases in trade with the GCC - contrary to the embargo placed on Egypt by the Arab League.

Step-by-step from 1981 through 1989, when Egypt was allowed back into the Arab League, each and every country in the Arab world, except Libya and Syria, circumvented the embargo. By 1989 the readmission of Egypt to the Arab League was like closing the barn door after the horse had been inside for years.

(Sullivan, 1999)

In summary, when faced with a rightfully critical Arab public, Western governments have to do everything in their power to avoid propagandistic connotations to their public diplomacy. This is best undertaken by securing the perception of legitimate intent through the pursuit of national interests, which simultaneously serve a broader shared purpose with the foreign public. The wave of demonstrations for democracy and universal human rights that resulted in the monumental ousting of Ben Ali in Tunisia and Mubarak in Egypt, and continued open demands for freedom across the region in the face of oppression, prove that these shared interests run deep. However, the intent to create a win-win situation on the basis of shared interests alone is not enough.

At the end of 2012 and in the first half of 2013, the security establishment and Egyptian society began to pose a challenge to the state's monopoly on the use of force. The growing polarization between the supporters of Morsi (that is, the rule of the Muslim Brotherhood) and his opponents and the public's dissatisfaction with the lack of real progress in realizing the goals of the revolution—especially social justice and better socioeconomic conditions—returned people to the streets. The struggle between the supporters of Morsi and his opponents

escalated and turned violent. Many protestors were killed or wounded during the rounds of violence that continued through most of 2013.

The violence peaked after Morsi's removal, with riots erupting throughout the country as Morsi supporters confronted the security forces, leading to the deaths of more than 1,150 demonstrators.

According to media reports and intelligence assessments in Egypt and elsewhere, these attacks were carried out by militant Islamists factions, some identified with the Muslim Brotherhood, which was outlawed after the coup, some with Wilayat Sinai, and some with ISIS members operating in Egypt at the organization's behest to expand the battle against Egypt's security forces from the Sinai Peninsula into Egypt proper. The security challenges that the various organizations posed to al-Sisi's regime embarrassed the president, the regime, and the security services, as they repeatedly highlighted the regime's weakness and its inability to ensure security and stability. In other words, al-Sisi's regime was failing in its attempt to subordinate the nation's territory to its authority, evident of the regime's failure to preserve its monopoly on the use of force in all parts of its sovereign territory (true as of 2018). During 2016, and even more so in 2017, terrorism turned downward, largely consequent to consistent suppression and more intelligence activity.

In the Sinai Peninsula, however, the regime has been less successful against Wilayat Sinai of the Islamic State. As of 2018, it seems that Egypt has succeeded in expanding its control of Sinai. In practice, however, Egypt had to take two steps in which it conceded its monopoly on the use of force: the first involved recruiting the Bedouin tribes in Sinai to fight Wilayat Sinai in exchange for military aid (weapons and fighting methods) and economic aid earmarked for the tribes. The second step was military cooperation with Israel. It was obvious that the regime was uncomfortable doing this and viewed it as a necessary evil given the circumstances and its own inability to independently regain its monopoly on the use of force in Sinai.

Egypt has tried to maintain a low profile on its military cooperation with Israel lest the legitimacy of the regime be called into question. In an investigative piece on the topic published by the New York Times in February 2018, Israel revealed it had carried out more than 100 attacks in northern Sinai in 2016 and 2017. Israel's missions, using fighter jets, helicopters, and UAVs bearing no Israeli insignia, were carried out with President al-Sisi's authorization. Although the publication included detailed descriptions of the Israeli raids shared by American and British sources, Egypt denied that anything like that had ever happened.

Presumably, Egypt's denial stemmed from its concern that this cooperation might cause additional damage to the regime's legitimacy and to al-Sisi, who was preparing for the new presidential election, which took place in March 2018. As noted, the regime's legitimacy was already in doubt and the election highlighted this further. One of the causes of the destabilization of a regime's legitimacy is the failure of the state to impose its monopoly over all of its territory and of the security forces to provide security and stability. It can be said that Egypt under al-Sisi acted against the classic notion of state logic in which the state preserves its monopoly on force within its borders. The

willingness to arm the Bedouin tribes in Sinai (and taking the risk that the weapons they now possess might one day be turned against state forces, as critics have pointed out) and, to some extent, to allow Israel to operate on Egyptian sovereign territory indicates that the regime recognizes its own weakness. Conceding its monopoly on force within its borders signifies weakness in one of the fundamental components of Egyptian stateness and has negative ramifications for the nation's security and stability.

(Van Doeveren, 2011)

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